

FAILURE MECHANISM OF A MULTI-LAYER COATING FOR THE OXIDATION PROTECTION OF C/C COMPOSITES

Laifei Cheng, Litong Zhang, Yongdong Xu

*State Key Laboratory of Solidification Processing,
Northwestern Polytechnical University, Xi'an Shaanxi 710072, P. R. China*

SUMMARY: A multi-layer coating for carbon-carbon composites (C/C) with a Si-W outer layer, a SiC barrier layer and a SiC transition layer was prepared by the combination of Siliconization, CVD and Liquid Reaction method. The oxidation experiments at from 1600°C to 1700°C were conducted. The coated C/C always gained in weight at beginning. When it started to loss in weight, deep holes could be observed on the coating surface. At this time, the thickness of the oxide film on the coating surface at different temperature was found to vary little. Thermochemical analysis shows that the gas pressure at the interface of the coating and its oxide film could be higher than the ambient pressure, and gas bubbles would be formed in the oxidation process. The nucleation, growth, bursting and self-sealing processes of the bubbles were studied.

KEY WORDS: C/C composites, coating, oxide film, failure mechanism

INTRODUCTION

Carbon-carbon composites (C/C) exhibit excellent structural properties above 1650°C, and are considered as the most promising candidate materials for the high thrust-weight ratio turbine engines. As a key technology for the high-temperature structural applications of C/C, oxidation protection is paid more and more attention recently. A number of studies have been conducted on the short-time oxidation protection, including various oxidation inhibitors, protection coating and sealants. For the long-time coating, not much progress has been made, in spite of years of intense effort. The study of failure mechanism is very important to the prolongation of protection life for a high-temperature coating and the development of a long-time protection coating system of C/C aimed at the components of advanced aircraft engines [1].

At above limiting use temperature, the coating will be destroyed entirely in a short time because of chemical compatibility of interfaces. At below cracking temperature, failure will take place at the coating-substrate interface because of oxygen diffusion through the cracking. At between intrinsic protection range temperature, failure is mainly influenced by the oxygen diffusion through the coating [2, 3]. Can we think simply the time obtained by dividing the coating thickness with the diffusion rate constant of oxygen at some temperature as the protection life at this temperature? In this paper, we will answer this question.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The substrate material used in experiments, cut off from aircraft brakes, is a 2D-C/C with a density of 1.7g/cm^3 . The substrates are of cubed shape with a size of $5\text{mm}\times 5\text{mm}\times 25\text{mm}$. The multi-layer coating consists of three layers. The SiC transition layer was prepared by Siliconazition on the surface of the substrates to decrease the interfacial mismatch and increase the adhesive strength. The SiC barrier layer was prepared on the transition layer by CVD to prevent carbon outward diffusion and out layer inward penetration[4]. The Si-W sealant layer was prepared by Liquid Reaction to provide an effective barrier to inward diffusion of oxygen. The purity of the Si and W powder used to prepare the transition and sealant layer is above 99.5%, and that of the MTS used in CVD is above 98%. The Si-W layer was prepared in a vacuum furnace in which the spreading out of the Si-W layer can be observed timely[5]. The work temperature and the vacuum of this furnace is respectively 1600°C and 0.0133Pa . Oxidation tests of long-time in dry air at 1600°C , 1650°C and 1700°C were conducted in a furnace heated with MoSi_2 rods. The thickness of the oxide film on the coating surface was identified with EMPA and SEM.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Because the coated C/C firstly gains and then losses in weight in the oxidation, the time the weight change is equal to zero can be defined as the protection life t_c , which can be called the critical protection life or effective protection time also.

The measured protection life at different temperature is listed in Table 1. It is shown that the relation curve of the protection life with temperature fits Arrhenius's law

$$\lg t_c = \frac{44104}{T} - 25.311 \quad (1)$$

Table1: Effect of temperature on the oxidation protection life

Temperature ($^\circ\text{C}$)	1600	1650	1700
Oxidation protection life (h)	168	30	4

When the oxidation time is beyond the critical protection life, the coated C/C losses in weight rapidly. This tells us that catastrophic oxidation has taken place. The catastrophic oxidation always starts from one or two points which appear to be black at high temperature. Deep holes will be formed at the black points which become the diffusion channel of oxygen. Fig.1 is the SEM micrograph of a deep hole on the coating surface.

It is not difficult to find that the deep holes are produced by escape of gas bubbles from their shape. The thermochemical diagram (Fig.2) shows that the gas pressure P_i at the interface of the coating and its oxide film can be higher than the ambient pressure, and gas bubbles will be formed in the oxidation process[6]. The gas products at the interface are mainly SiO. Partial pressure of the oxides of W is negligible. They dissolve in the oxide film, and then diffuse

towards the surface, and run away at last (Fig.3). The W dissolved in the liquid Si increases the interfacial gas pressure greatly.

The high-valence W ion is a glass former. It will get into the molecule net of the silica and make the oxide film become silica glass in the oxidation process (Fig.4 and Fig.5). From Raman spectrum of the oxide film, we know that the silica glass is highly stable in more than one hundred hours (Table 2). Formation of silica glass layer is very important to the long-term coating. Of course, glass layer will drop its using temperature.

Because the oxide film is thinner and resists to the nucleation and bursting of the gas bubbles less at the beginning of oxidation, more bubbles will be formed. The holes leaved on the oxide film by bursting of gas bubbles is smaller and less shallow. They will be sealed fastly by the viscous flow of glass. The longer of the oxidation time, the thicker the oxide film and the larger the resistance, then the more difficult for the bubbles to nucleate. Consequently, The bubbles formed are fewer, and greater and deeper when they burst. At some temperature, the viscous flow is limited. When the bubbles are large enough so that they can not be sealed in time, holes appear on the oxide film. At the same time, new oxide film is formed at the holes. Obviously, bubbles will prior necleate, grow and burst at the holes in further oxidation as the new film formed is very thin. As a result, the holes get deeper and deeper. When they penetrate through the coating at last, failure takes place. The failure precess is summarizd in Fig.6.

Fig.1: SEM micrograph of a deep hole on the coating surface

Fig.2 Thermochemical diagram for the W-Si-O system at 1873 K

Fig.3 Distribution of W ion on the coating after oxidation for 168 h at 1600 °C

Fig.4: X-ray diffraction pattern of the coating after oxidation

Fig.5: SEM micrograph of the coating after oxidation

1. C/C; 2. Transition layer; 3. Barrier layer; 4. Si-W layer; 5. Silica layer

Table 2: The effect of oxidation time on the network structure of the silica glass formed on the coating surface after oxidation at 1600°C

Oxidation time /h	Composition of the molecule network structure /%				Broken bonds /%
	Dimer	Sheet	Network	Pure network	
Before oxidation	22	0	34	44	18.5
45	21	0	69	10	19.9
168	16	11	30	43	16.6

Fig.6: The failure process of the coating in oxidation

If the analysis about the failure process is correct, there certainly is a critical oxide thickness $X(t_c)$, corresponding to the critical life. That is to say, the oxide thickness when the coating fails depends on the diffusion rate constant and has nothing to do with temperature. Relation of the critical thickness with the critical life fits a parabolic law [7,8].

Fig 7: Distribution of oxygen ion on the coating after oxidation for 168h at 1600 °C

$$X(t_c) = \sqrt{Bt_c} \tag{2}$$

For this coating, the critical thickness of the oxide film is founded to be always 40 μm less or more at different oxidation temperature (Fig.7). On the basis of critical thickness, we can obtain a relation of the critical life with temperature as following

$$\lg t_c = \frac{44104}{T} - 25.340 \quad (3)$$

This relation calculated is identical with the that put forward derrectly from the oxidation tests. This demonstrates clearly the failure mechanism presented.

It is meant by $X(t)_C$ that a coating would fail because some defects are formed when the thickness of the film reaches its critical value. $X(t)_C$ is a constant which is only influenced by the coating materials, coating structure, coating method and coating process, but not related to the oxidation temperature. The properties of the coating materials determine the characteristics of the oxide film and the interfacial gas pressure. The critical thickness of the film increases with increasing the interfacial gas pressure, decreasing the diffusion rate of oxygen and increasing the diffusion rate of gas species. In the presence of a barrier layer in the coating, the diffusion of oxygen along the deep holes would be blocked, and the critical thickness of the film would be increased. Deep holes could be considered to be formed at the sites where there are some original defects. Obviously, the defects are conditioned by the non-homogeneity of the coating preparation. Consequently, improving homogeneity of the coating is a very effective way to increase the critical thickness and prolong the protection life. After the coating materials are selected, the critical thickness depends upon the quality of the multi-layer coating. Only proper methods are selected or developed to prepare every layer of the multi-layer coating, the quality could be ensured. Although the interfacial gas pressure varies with temperature, the limited step of the interfacial gas reaction is the diffusion rate but not the reaction rate. Clearly, it is the diffusion rate constant but not the critical thickness that is influenced by temperature. Generally, the viscosity of the oxide film drops when temperature rises. The viscosity drop, on the one hand, makes the holes easy to be sealed and is favorable to increasing the critical thickness. On the other hand, it promotes the nucleation and growth of bubbles, and unfavorable to increasing the critical thickness. It can be argued that viscosity has not influence on the critical thickness in a certain range of temperature.

CONCLUSIONS

1. The gases produced by the interfacial reaction between the outer layer and its oxide film are responsible for the coating failure. When the gas pressure is higher than the ambient, bubbles are formed at the interface.
2. The oxide film is a silica glass. When the bubbles are large enough that holes caused by their bursting can not be sealed in time, non-homogeneous nucleation, growth and bursting of the gas bubbles take place at the holes in further oxidation. As a result, deep holes are formed, which will become the channel of oxygen diffusion.
3. It is the critical thickness of the oxide film but not the coating thickness that affects the oxidation protection life. The relation of the protection life obtained from experiments is highly identical with that calculated based on the critical thickness.

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REFERENCES

1. Deborah, D. L., *Carbon Fiber Composites*, Butterworth-Heinemann, London, 1993
2. Strife, J. R., Sheehan, J. E., "Ceramic Coating for Carbon-Carbon Composites", *Ceramic Bulletin*, Vol.67, No.2, 1988, pp. 369-374
3. Luthra, K. L., "Oxidation of Carbon-Carbon Composites—A Theoretical Analysis", *Carbon* Vol.26, No.2, 1988, pp. 217-224
4. Yongdong, Xu, Litong, ZHANG and Laifei, CHENG, "Three Dimensional Carbon Fiber Reinforced Silicon Carbide Composites Prepared By Chemical Vapor Infiltration", *J. Chinese Ceramic Society*, Vol.24, No.5, 1996, pp. 485-489
5. Litong, ZHANG, Laifei, CHENG, "Measurements for the Wetting Angel Between Ceramics and Metals", *Yuhang Cailiao Gongyi*, No.99, 1988, pp. 49£55
6. Knacke, O., Kubaschewski, O. and Hwsselmann, K., *Thermochemical Properties of Inorganic Substance*, Heidelberg, Berlin, 1991
7. Deal, B, E., "General Relationship for the Thermal Oxidation of Silicon", *J. Appl. Phys.*, Vol.36 ,No.12, 1965, pp. 3770£78
8. Schiroky, G. H., "Oxidation Behavior of Chemically Vapor-Deposited Silicon Carbide", *Advanced Ceramic Materials*, Vol. 2, No.2, 1987, pp. 137£141